

Environmental trade-offs of reclaimed asphalt pavement under different destination scenarios using system expansion

Supporting Information

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From	To	Distance, km	Type of transport	Emission standard
Oil refinery	Asphalt binder modifier	146	Lorry (> 32 t)	EURO 3
Tyre supplier	Asphalt binder modifier	45	Lorry (16 – 32 t)	EURO 3
Asphalt binder modifier	Mixing plant	214	Lorry (> 32 t)	EURO 3
Gravel supplier	Mixing plant	1	Lorry (16 – 32 t)	EURO 3

Table S1. Transport information

*1 kWh is equivalent to 3.6 MJ, measured electricity consumption: 1.2 kWh/t

Process	Energy source	Source calorific value, MJ/kg	Theoretical heat energy per t, MJ/t	
			ORAP	50RAP
Bitumen storage	Gas (LPG)	46.5	20	13
Virgin aggregate drying and heat	Gas (LPG)	46.5	279	221
RAP drying and heat	-	-	0	0
Asphalt mixture mixing	Electricity*	-	-	-
Total energy required from plant, MJ/t	-	-	300	234

Table S2. Theoretical energy demand calculated considering materials' temperatures and heating capacity (see Table S4)

*gravel data collected in Brazilian quarries by IPT (Institute for Technological Research)

Phase/scenarios	Unit process	Description	Data source
Raw material productions	Crumb rubber (CR)	Waste tires processing modeled according to literature data	Tushar et al. (2022) and ecoinvent 3.5: Electricity, medium voltage {BR} market for Cut-off, U; Diesel, burned in building machine {GLO} market for Cut-off, U
	Neat asphalt binder	Virgin asphalt binder	Ecoinvent 3.5: Pitch {RoW} petroleum refinery operation Cut-off,U
	Aggregate	Virgin aggregate	IPT and ecoinvent 3.5: Gravel, crushed {BR} production*
	Lime	-	Ecoinvent 3.5: Lime, hydrated, packed {GLO} market for Cut-off, U
Material transportations	CR asphalt, aggregate, and lime	Transportation by truck	Ecoinvent 3.5: Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO3 {RoW} transport, freight, lorry 16-32 or lorry >32 metric ton, EURO3 Cut-off, U
Asphalt mix manufacturing	Pavement HMA surface layer (road A rehabilitation)	Consumption of LPG and electricity based on theoretical energy demand Table S2 (Santos et al., 2018)	Ecoinvent 3.5: Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas {RoW} heat production, propane, at industrial furnace >100kW Cut-off, U, and Electricity, medium voltage {BR} market for Cut-off, U
Landfill (S1)	RAP landfilling	Pavement waste	Waste asphalt {RoW} treatment of, sanitary landfill Cut-off, U
Alternative pavement gravel layer (S2)	RAP downcycling in road B gravel layer	Used as alternative aggregate to gravel pavement layer	-
RAP processing to recycle and alternative pavement gravel layer(S3)	RAP recycling (50% RAP)	Used for partial substitution of asphalt binder and aggregates in new asphalt mix surface layer. RAP processing by crushing	Ecoinvent 3.5: Machine operation, diesel, >= 74.57 kW, high load factor {GLO} market for Cut-off, U
	RAP downcycling in road B gravel layer	Used as alternative aggregate to gravel pavement layer. Supply of virgin aggregate would be necessary to build the same 1,8 km length of road B gravel layer	IPT and ecoinvent 3.5: Gravel, crushed {BR} production*

Table S3. Life cycle inventory

*Final temperature estimated according to the Asphalt Institute (2015). T: temperature

Process	Asphalt mix 0 RAP		Asphalt mix 50 RAP		Energy source	Heat capacity (kJ/C/kg)	Unit	Asphalt mix 0 RAP	Asphalt mix 50 RAP
	Initial T, °C	Final T, °C	Initial T, °C	Final T, °C				mass functional unit (kg)	mass functional unit (kg)
Bitumen storage	20	170	20	170	Gas (LPG)	2.093	KJ/Kg/C	69274	44870
Virgin aggregate (drying and heating)	20	180	20	210*	Gas (LPG)	0.79	KJ/Kg/C	1270020	659034
RAP (drying and heating)	20	20	20	20	-	-	-	0	678665
Asphalt mixture	170	170	170	170	Electricity	-	-	1358310	1402200
Water 4%	20	100	20	100		4.1855	KJ/Kg/C	50801	53508
Water vapor	100	180	100	210		1.83	KJ/Kg	50801	53508
Latent heat of water evaporation						2256	KJ/Kg		
Casing loses factor						0.27			

Table S4. Temperatures during mixing phase, mass and heat capacity of each asphalt mixture material

References

- Asphalt Institute (2015). Mix design methods for asphalt concrete and other hot-mix types. MS-2. Lexington, KY, USA.
- Santos, J., Bressi, S., Cerezo, V., Presti, D.L., Dauvergne, M., 2018. Life cycle assessment of low temperature asphalt mixtures for road pavement surfaces: A comparative analysis. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 138, 283-297.
- Tushar, Q., Santos, J., Zhang, G., Bhuiyan, M. A., Giustozzi, F., 2022. Recycling waste vehicle tyres into crumb rubber and the transition to renewable energy sources: A comprehensive life cycle assessment. *J. Environ. Manag.* 323, 116289.